

A The Searching for Increasing the Steel Producing Amount with USA France & West Germany etc. & Brazil Motor Sale Amount in January 2026 through Sustainability

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ABSTRACT: The GDP as an indicating economy would have a significant effect, so that the variation status might influence the whole national economic level & quality gradually because the China already entered into the 13 ten thousand dollars threshold that will be a developing milestone. We should continue to develop to 20 ten thousand dollars one sustainably through utilizing our nation people wisdom and behavior. It is believed that after ten year the new era can be open for us to experience and share. At the same time, the new quality productivity will become an indication direction that can be cultivated from now on so as to acquire a high-technology & high-sustainability one. Like Winder turbine, Photovoltaic voltage, nuclear-reaction piles, low-air economy etc that definitely can bring out new innovation behavior for instructing further advanced technology. Thereby, the high-tech production would occupy the most part for us to pursue the high-efficiency and high-level environment that might become our further destination for producing more innovation production continually. So that the enough educating new engineer and talents enable us to process more space for searching more functional ones with more diversities business.

Because those diversities may make our life to become more convenient and comfortable through endeavoring our engineers

and experts for the sake of positively participating their each research theme and making an interesting conception under main principles. In USA the more sophisticated project will affect their GDP enhancement through widely collecting the world top scientists and scholars to process more deepening research and science that may occupy their first-one country with stabilized leading effectiveness. From California to Missouri state the higher GDP would reflect the entire nation quality and level through the aeronautics out-space exploration lunar landing etc. a series of scientific research are able to continually process that makes the USA to become No. 1 in mostly all of the fields. Even they proceeded the Mars etc. approaching and rotating & landing works many years ago. Moreover, they owned the most amount nuclear weapons with several thousands that may destroy the whole earth once the nuclear war happens. So we should pay more attention to the USA who may affect its role in every aspects in the earth. Thereby, China will raise up becoming the second GDP big country who may prohibit USA military and limit its development and enlarging behavior too.

Keywords: *Searching for, USA, France & West Germany etc., steel producing amount, the auto sale amount variation in Brazil, sustainability*

1. Introduction

The GDP which indicates national economic status has provided an important role in every aspect in the world. So that the population increasing rate would be maintained for the sake of raising high-technique product with the entire industrial chain constantly which might enhance our new-quality-productivity. Hence we should consider the effective factors for example the population quantity, new quality productivity with high-technique etc. like big plane electric vehicle battery AI robot quantum computer medicine making disease diagnosis AI (artificial intelligence) ocean source space exploration nuclear generator etc. other ones. Low population is enable to offer high life & quality with improving GDP per capita value. Meanwhile, it can enhance the national whole GDP value and help us to boost the economic recovery and many things to do. So the certain population is about to improve our

national confidence some degree and make us to become priority one as early as possible even the super-country to lead the world to leadership right.

In contrast, the GDP increasing rate may play a significant role with regulating population increasing rate mutually and cooperatively. Hence the two aspects may be emphasized and paid attention to in thriving the whole national economic developed degree through enough wielding our generations positively and efficiently by our government institution endeavor and evaluation. For the sake of making relevant policies and allocating capital into the necessary industries the corresponding strategic plan needs to be made under various background and entities. Then the according monitor and estimation will be followed and estimated periodically and frequently by the observer in government's institution. At last as to the developed speed in one nation the corresponding population increasing quantity and high-technique product producing will be discussed and considered more preciously and correctly according to the near past years experience and variation.

Therefore, the high-technique products will be completed through wielding our scientist & senior Engineers coordination tightly for the sake of reviving the industrial and tertiary modernization. We should constantly look for and seek the new quality productivity sustainably so as to take place of our traditional industry becoming modernity. An innovation industry like new energy electric generator will be in front of our path forwards, so that the corresponding tactic must be put up and seek the opportunity and fortune in order to burden our responsibility quickly and not to forget recommend the fitting one to appoint new occupation. Like the Bole identified horse or Maosui self-recommended the recommendation will be represent one aspect for our human resource department to consider and evaluate the recommended included a full research room with a set of computer high-technique instrument & device, subordinate, subsidiary staff, salary, house, welfare etc. a series of work so as to appoint his new occupation reasonably and willingly. [1~15]

2. Discussions

For the sake of welcoming the demand we should educate a lot of scientist and experts candidates from university department to college & institution one to take the high scholar degree for them to grasp one foreign language and skill to apply to

futural requirement and practice. In university, the class with taking more practice education and experience and good teacher proceed the more competition teaching and theoretical and practical combination class to prepare for using after their graduate from college. Meantime, the enhancing GDP factors will include the high-technique products and its whole industrial chains and high-intelligence product that may influence the service business mostly. So we should increase those high-profit & high-tech skill for making more advance products so as to improve our service business level and quality & effectiveness at all. So that we should maintain and develop the tertiary industry continuously under controlling the second one. With the life quality enhancing continually the service one is about to wield its effectiveness presently and in futural long time, thereby we should follow up the changed situation and own independent capacity to master one outstanding skill to satisfy the futural request in advance. [16~20]

2.1 The steel producing amount analysis

The steel producing amount analysis in 1974~1987 would show 80 & 18 million tons by USA & France accordingly expressed the USA strong steel producing capacity in 1987 in light of Figure 1. The y-y value might indicate -2% & -2.5% by them accordingly recorded their minus growth speed.

Figure 1 The steel producing amount analysis in 1974~1987. [1]

The steel producing amount analysis in 1974~1987 would show 56 & 8 million tons by China & East Germany accordingly expressed the China strong steel producing

capacity in 1987 in light of Figure 2. The y-y value might indicate -2% & -2.5% by them accordingly recorded their minus growth speed.

Figure 2 The steel producing amount analysis I in 1974~1987. [1]

Moreover, the steel producing amount analysis in 1981~1983 would show 41 & 7 million tons by China & East Germany accordingly expressed the China strong steel producing capacity in 1983 in light of Figure 3. The y-y value might indicate 8% & -0.6% by them accordingly recorded their moderate & minus growth speed respectively.

Figure 3 The steel producing amount analysis in 1981~1983. [1]

At the end, the steel producing amount analysis in 1981~1983 would show 100 & 18 million tons by Japan & France accordingly expressed the Japan & USA with 79 million

tons strong steel producing capacity in 1983 in light of Figure 4. The y-y value might indicate -0.5% & -7% by them accordingly recorded their minus growth speed.

Figure 4 The steel producing amount analysis I in 1981~1983. [1]

2.3 Brazil motor sale amount analysis in January, 2026

The Brazil top motor Brands' sale amount analysis in January, 2026 would show 3.5~9 thousand by Caoa Chery~Toyota maker respectively explained the Honda with 6.7 thousand to follow Toyota occupying the second position whilst the Toyota exhibited strong motor producing capacity in light of Figure 5. Thereby, the above two exceeded the average 5.6 thousand ones.

Figure 5 The Brazil top motor Brands' sale amount analysis in January, 2026. [2]

The Brazil top motor Brands' sale market share analysis in January, 2026 would show 2.2%~5.9% by Caoa Chery~Toyota maker respectively explained their modest

growth in light of Figure 6. Thereby, the Toyota & Honda exceeded the average 3.4% with the forward speed.

Figure 6 The Brazil top motor Brands' market share analysis in January 2026.[2]

3. Conclusions

The GDP as an indicating economy would have a significant effect, so that the variation status might influence the whole national economic level & quality gradually because the China already entered into the 13 ten thousand dollars threshold that will be a developing milestone. We should continue to develop to 20 ten thousand dollars one sustainably through utilizing our nation people wisdom and behavior. It is believed that after ten year the new era can be open for us to experience and share. At the same time, the new quality productivity will become an indication direction that can be cultivated from now on so as to acquire a high-technology & high-sustainability one. Like Winder turbine, Photovoltaic voltage, nuclear-reaction piles, low-air economy etc that definitely can bring out new innovation behavior for instructing further advanced technology. Thereby, the high-tech production would occupy the most part for us to pursue the high-efficiency and high-level environment that might become our further destination for producing more innovation production continually. So that the enough educating new engineer and talents enable us to process more space for searching more functional ones with more diversities business. Because those diversities may make our life to become more convenient and comfortable through endeavoring our engineers and experts for the sake of positively participating their each research theme and making an

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Ethic Declarations

The authors declared that there were not conflicts of interest.

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